

THE IMPERATIVE OF TEACHERS' CORE DUTIES IN SHAPING SUSTAINABLE HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM PRACTICES

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Abstract: *The paper examines the role of teacher in the Nigeria context is circumscribed by the objective of social transformation as articulated in the Nigeria constitution in the Fundamental Rights and in the Directive Principles of State Policy Extension which is the additional dimension of Professional practice among teachers at higher education can be used as a revolutionary tool to modify the existing slogan of 'education for all', thereby making the 'life-long education', a reality. This conceptual paper addresses the needs of preparing the students for individual growth as also to facilitate them to contribute to social development. The paper also focuses on the inclusion of the measures required to be taken for providing social consciousness and sensitivity, as happens to be a neglected part of the curriculum. The extra effort so needed to build community-based activities presupposes the requirement for professional training to be given to the hospitality and tourism educators or teachers as a continuing education initiative.*

Keywords: *Extension Education, Holistic Curriculum, Hospitality and Tourism Teachers.*

1. Introduction

The phrase holistic curriculum 'needs to be understood as a comprehensive effort to provide skills and competences required for leading the life of a responsible citizen with concern for fellow beings. Generally, job market-oriented curriculum aims to provide living skills i.e. only those skills required for earning a livelihood. This holistic curriculum concept is in conformity with the National University Commission '(a statutory body of the Government of Nigeria for the coordination, determination and maintenance of standards of university education in Nigeria) directive regarding threefold duties of a university of providing domain knowledge, getting involved in research and participating in community-

oriented extension activities. The extension activities refer to those activities which are taken amidst the community set up to improve the quality of life of members of a community. Extension education on the other hand, is largely the process of teaching rural people how to live better by learning ways to improve their livelihood, home and community institutions. It is helping people to help themselves 'by changing their behavior (knowledge, attitude and skills). It is the challenge of capacity building for socio-economic development of a community: the change is carried out by formulating activities involving the community (Sanyal, 2005).

We shall examine the issues mentioned above in the light of generalized picture of contemporary High Education in Nigeria; the establishment aim of the UN posited Education for sustainable development (2005-2014) that education embracing sustainable development must share the characteristics of learning and teaching should model the values of sustainable development.

These include: 1. Respect for the dignity and human rights of people throughout the world and a commitment to social and economic justice for all. 2. Respect for the human rights of future generations and a commitment to intergenerational responsibility. 3. Respect and care for the great community of life in all its diversity which involves the protection and restoration of the earth 's ecosystem. 4. Respect for cultural diversity and a commitment to build locally and globally a culture of tolerance, non-violence and peace (UNESCO, 2006:16).

According to *Bertrand Arthur William Russell*, the aims of education are to build vitality, courage, sensitiveness and intelligence in the individuals. Vitality indicates capability of education to cultivate a concern for the society, to create a sense of objectivity and to enhance power of hard work. –Courage refers to the combination of self-respect and an imperial outlook on life. Sensitiveness implies that education facilities appropriate emotional response for the events around, which could be the precursor for any remedial action to be taken for the benefit of the society. Hence, there is need for teachers to redefine their primary responsibilities to improve quality education for sustainable development; they also need to carry out teaching, counseling and research to improve quality education in the higher institutions of learning. –Intelligence refers to actual knowledge, willingness to accept knowledge and curiosity to look up to various sources. Another perspective is given by the –United Nations Educational Scientific and cultural Organization (UNESCO) Report of the international commission on Education for the twenty-first century, learning: states that education is based on four pillars learning to know, learning to do, learning to live together and learning to be.

i. Learning to know by combining a sufficiently broad general knowledge with the opportunity to work in depth on a small number of subjects. This also means learning to learn, so as to benefit from the opportunity's education provides throughout life. ii. Learning to do, in order to acquire not only an occupational skill but also, more broadly the competence to deal with many situations and work in teams. It also means learning to do in the context of young people 's various social and work experiences which may be informal, as a result of the local or national context, or formal, involving courses alternatively study and work.

iii. Learning to live, by developing an understanding of other people and an appreciation of interdependence-carrying out projects and learning to manage conflicts – in a spirit of respect for the values of pluralism, mutual understanding and peace.

iv. Learning to be, so as to develop one 's personality and be able to act with ever greater autonomy, judgment and personal responsibility. In that connection, education must not disregard any aspect of a person 's potential, memory, reasoning, physical capacities and communication skills.

The decors report further states Formal education systems tends to emphasize the acquisition of knowledge to the detriment of other types of learning; but it is vital now to conceive education in a more encompassing fashion. Such a vision should inform and guide future educational reforms and policy, in relation both to contents and to methods; while discussing as to what education should achieve, the preamble of Nigerian Constitution policy on education has much relevance. Nigerian constitution lay down the political structure for governance along with specification of citizen 's rights and duties in

order to ensure justice, liberty, equality and fraternity for one and all. The educational curriculum needs to reinforce the spirit of constitution. In the light of the above, the discussion can serve to sensitize us as to what should curriculum be, if it is to contribute to the wholesome development of the individuals.

2. Objectives

This paper is an attempt to accomplish the following objectives

- i. To explore the need of extension activities as part of the hospitality & tourism management curriculum in Nigeria.
- ii. TO contemplate the integration between students and the local community by means of educational and curriculum advancement.
- iii. TO identify the desirable characteristics required by the Hospitality & Tourism Educators to be the administrators for extension education.

3. Context of the study

The paper suggests the inclusion of the measures required to be taken for providing social consciousness and sensitivity, as this happens to be a neglected part of the curriculum. It also focuses on the twin needs of preparing the students for individual growth as also to facilitate them to contribute to the social development. The education should bring about holistic development of the learners including awareness about the community and the environment.

4. Definition of Terms

4.1 Extension activities/education: According to Saville (1965), the aim of all extension work is to teach rural people how to raise their standard of living, but with minimum of assistance from government, and by their own efforts, using their own resources. It encourages progressive growth through local leadership, self-help, and civic pride. Fenley and William (1964) offer a definition: Extension education brings about improvement in a systematic way, through carefully planned and organized programmes. Extension education is voluntary; carried on out of school: directed to adult; concerned with their livelihood. Based on sound principles of teaching and learning, it is carried on thoughtfully and systematically in an atmosphere of mutual trust and respect. Extension therefore has three basic tasks: i. Disseminating useful information ii. Applying it to the analysis of practical problems and iii. Helping people to use it to help themselves.

4.2 Curriculum: Oxford Advanced Learner 's Dictionary define curriculum as the subjects that are included in a course of study or taught in a school, college, and it is a metaphor an educational course to be taught or learned. Still the dynamic nature of curriculum is implied. Generally, the word curriculum is considered to refer to course syllabus as approved by statutory bodies. Actually, it has a wider meaning. Curriculum refers to syllabi, print and electronic media materials teaching strategies, learning activities, assessments of the students, evaluation of syllabus, the classrooms, laboratories and library facilities, staff training and consultancy and so on.

4.3 Continuing Education: This is the learning activities of educating or instructing the professionals by impairing up-to-date knowledge or skills in a particular area beyond their basic literacy education. It is also often termed as __ further education 'or adult education. Constantly striving to learn about new and evolving knowledge or to review existing concepts and techniques is termed as continuing Education:

5. Literature Review

Hospitality and Tourism has been known as the world 's largest and fastest growing industry. This fast growth means that tourism constitutes a major feature of world economy and can thus act as a tool for poverty reduction in developing countries (Dieke, 2003) several conduct studies indicate that tourism has a significant economic, social and environmental effect at both macro and micro levels (Buckly, 2004; Georsa, 2003; Muhama 2007; Torres and Momsen, 2004). The possibility of tourism having the varying levels re-flexibility to think with other sectors makes it an industry capable of pulling an economy out of poverty (Sinclair, 2003). In order to enhance the community participation in tourism, and at the same time the quality of tourism services, governments have to undertake action for the provision of adequate educational, technical and professional training programmes, Relly and Koch (2002) showed that tourism education should be extended to school children so that they can appreciate, right from childhood, the wonders of nature. Moreover, training and education can be done in several areas such as communication, environmental health, nature conservation, business, traffic safety, motor mechanics and social work Relly and Koch, (2002).

Watson and Drummond (2002) commended that tourism has significant linkages with other sectors and training the people that run the industry is an integral part of its development. They reported that tourism training and education helps to improve attitude, enthusiasm and involvement of stakeholders in tourism development. Hanquin and Terry (2004) suggested that for training to be done a thorough environment analysis should be done to develop a general strategies direction for human resource development. In order to create indigenious capabilities, they proposed on-the-job training; training of the trainers; and certifying educators and improving research skills.

Howel and Uysal (1987) emphasized that developing countries need professionals who have a holistic perception of the industry, people who are able to understand it as a whole, its interrelationships, and its impact, and professionals who are able to find a way to avoid the inadequate forms of development of tourism within a country.

Throughout history extension education has focused on topics typically associated with being an extension agent, such as program planning and evaluation. Legacy and Wells (1987) found experienced agents identified program planning, evaluation, and the development of media presentations as the three most important instructional items for extension education. The most important topics for internship preparation were considered to be program planning and maintenance, committee involvement, and personal visits.

The lack of research directed toward extension education curriculum may be because the need for such a program is misunderstood. The written position descriptions for open extension position frequently describe a desire for applicants with degrees in programmatic fields other than extension education; rarely is a degree in extension education specifically identified as desirable (National Job Bank, 2008). Adult education and volunteer management are two such skill area closely associated with employment in cooperative extension (Franz, 2007; Scheising & Safrit, 2007).

6. Importance of community-oriented activities as part of curriculum

According to Sheer, Ferrari, Earnest, and Connors (2006). –Developing and revising academic programs must be an ongoing process|. Extension education should be exempt from such scrutiny. Formal extension education programs can play an Integral role in developing students 'job skills by

providing a curriculum uniquely tailored to the competencies required of extension professionals. According to Kelly (2004), curriculum is –the overall rationale for any educational program.

The recruitment agencies often make a point that there is a need to improve the skills and competences of the graduates and technically/professionally trained manpower produced by the university system both at the entry level as also after employment. Each industry has its own requirement of skills and competences for recruitment and, their relative importance is also different. Mostly the university system concentrates on domain knowledge and less weight is given to other skills and competences such as soft skills, social skills, etc. in keeping with the preamble to the Indian constitution, it is essential given attention to social skills, especially in the areas of community-oriented activities and participation in community development. Such an approach is needed to foster in student a sense of

- a. Justice in terms of social, economic and political aspects;
- b. Equality of status among all the components of a society and
- c. Fraternity assuring the dignity of the individual and the unity and integrity of the nation.

One of the educational purposes is to maintain its social relevance. It reflects the kind of value system the institution desires to inculcate in its students and its willingness to play the role as instrument of change for economic development and social transformation. The community related sensitivity needs to be developed right from school days and, more so, during the period of college study, as this alone could serve as the basis for lifelong social involvement. It addresses the concern for learning to live together, which is essential for peaceful coexistence in a nation and overall development. The activities help in building self esteem by promoting a sense of concern for fellow beings, team spirit, the value of interdependence, problem solving skills, communication power, etc. The scheme also permits percolation of traits of tolerance, respect for local culture, understanding of the rights of individual citizens, appreciation of aesthetic beauty of unrecognized sectors etc. The initiative fosters a creative desire for service and empathy in the students.

The preceding discussion shows that getting involved in community work is one of the methods of bringing about an attitudinal change, which is generally quite difficult to attain. Attitude comes under the realms of affective domain. According to Bloom 's Taxonomy, affective domain contains five levels: Receiving, Responding, Valuing, Organization and Characterization by value. The level one, __receiving 'refers to the willingness to receive information or to attend to particular phenomena or stimuli in the domain of feelings or emotions. Receiving also refers to actively attending to an act. The level two responding refers to active participation on the part of the student.

7. Extension Activities as Components of Vocational Education

Extension education is democratic in its approach. It is based on the principle of helping people to help themselves. The extension approach to economic development is. First, develop the people, and they will develop their community, their educational and recreational institutions, their public services and anything else they wish. That the inclusion of community-oriented activities strengthens the classification of the Hospitality and Tourism sector based educational initiatives as vocational courses could become evident, if we consider the views of

Miomir Despotovic. Iskra Maksimovic and Aleksandra Pejatovic. According to them, any vocational or adult (or community) education course needs to have the following components: accessibility, integration and partnership.

Accessibility Capacity building should be one of the objectives of education. It must foster the necessary knowledge, skills, competencies and values to all the stakeholders. In this knowledge era, it is an acclaimed fact that access and equity are needed to bring socio-economic development.

Integration The institutions should have an integrated approach of offering Courses, so that it could open up possibilities of widening intellectual, social and professional development of individuals concerned. By integration, we also refer to a wide canvass of teaching – learning methods.

Partnership - The educational institutions need to play a key role in partnering with different wings of the Government (such as Tourism. Labor. IIRI). Environment & forests etc.). Hotel Management and Tour Operators" associations, and their employees, NGOs. labor organizations etc. The academic activities need to be planned with the active participation of the stake holders.

8. Context for the Community Oriented Activities in Hospitality and Tourism Institutions

The term extension was first used to describe adult education programs in England in the second half of the 19th century. These programs helped to extend the work of universities outside the campus and into the neighboring communities. The term was later adopted in the USA. While in Britain it was replaced with advisory service in the 20th century. Numerous other terms are used in different parts of the world to describe the same or a similar concept (Wikipedia. 2008).

The extension activities could be

- (i) related to the domain of knowledge in the Hospitality and Tourism sectors or
- (ii) a development-oriented activity in a community set-up such as adult literacy, environmental protection. AIDS awareness, etc. or
- (iii) a training programme towards disaster or emergency management support (which would be needed during times of natural or manmade calamities).

The extension activities could be planned in the form of provision of job-related skill training to the underprivileged, the unemployed and unskilled sections of the society, destitute women and the prisoners so that they could secure means of living. There is a need to involve other segments of society like the community leaders. Prison Authorities. NGOs. Self-help groups, Social Welfare Organizations etc. to support the activities.

Considering that an academic year has around 200 days of academic activities, an institution is left with considerable time to fulfill its social obligations. The academic expertise, infrastructural and facilities, etc. are valuable institutional resources to meet the demands of skill training in non-formal wings of Hospitality and Tourism sectors. We shall illustrate community-based activities related to domain knowledge in Hospitality and Tourism disciplines:

9.1 Hospitality, for instance, deals with one of the three basic needs of human beings, namely food. The implication is that a large scope exists in selecting community development-oriented activities. The activities could be of the following types: skill training camp from any of the hospitality related fields such as Food Production. Food & Beverage Service, House Keeping.

Bakery & Confectionery. Owners and staffs of road side-dhabas (*food stalls*) and motels could be trained on hygiene & sanitation aspects of food, balanced diet, budgeting and account keeping, legal literacy etc.

10. Successive Stages for the Community Based Activities

The start is to be done with planning of the series of activities to be undertaken. The sequence of actions could be examined as follows:

Currying out need analysis

An elaborate exercise has to be undertaken to gather necessary information about the characteristics of the target clientele, local needs, cultural aspects, community or segment leaders to be consulted, etc. Opinion from experts, peer groups, NGOs and the target group will also be of help in organizing the activities.

11.1 Matching the activities with resource requirement

A list of activities planned and the resources available from the institution, community and support groups is to be prepared. The gaps in resources are to be identified along with remedial actions. Monetary requirements should be modest and within reach. The list should take into account the student and target population size which are going to be involved and the time factor as well. Prior training also needs to be planned for preparing the students with effective communication and interpersonal skills. Motivation strategy needs to be in-built. As part of the activities, debate, music, humor session, dramatization, folk dances etc. could also be included to provide a variety in which the students, teachers and the target group could participate.

Team formation and execution

The activities should be classified and group responsibilities are to be assigned towards each of the components. Due weight must be given for planning, execution and evaluation of the activities. Even at the time of formulating the objectives, the performance indicators also should be incorporated into the scheme. The college students may exhibit distinct areas of intelligence - such as linguistic, logical, spatial kinesthetic, musical, emotional, interpersonal and naturalistic. While building teams, these aspects need to be kept in mind for effective execution of the plan.

Preparing evaluation report

Towards the end of the activities, the evaluation of the effectiveness of the activities is to be carried out. It gives valuable lessons as to how best the activities can be modified. The documentation could help in providing an improved model during future initiatives.

Showcasing the skills developed

In case specific skill inculcation programme is carried out with a segment of the community, it is worth while helping the group in exploring or suggesting suitable employment opening, so that an honorable livelihood could be secured. In certain cases, organizing community-based events or exhibitions also could be a morale booster for the trained group. Christ College, Bangalore provided training to a batch of street children in Hospitality related activities: it resulted in employment to a lot of them.

Student certification

As an incentive and morale booster, the students need to be given certificate for participation; in case of innovative contribution, it can be suitably rewarded.

Desirable Characteristics of Educators as Administrators of Extension Activities

In a developing society like India, institutions of higher learning have also an active role in evolving and maintaining a highly functional and dynamic link with the community. Creation of excellence is not the only goal of such institutions: it is perceived as an additional legitimate objective of an institution of higher education in a country like India to assume the status of a pivotal or nodal agency or a nucleus of the overall development of the community in which such institution exists. Educator in such institutions therefore has an additional duty of making available his or her expertise for the

development of various sectors of the community. Increasingly, educators or teachers are also expected to use their expertise in matters of national importance like nation building.

The values ascribed to academic profession by "The National Commission on Teachers" (**Government of India**) have much significance in running Extension Activities:

- Acquisition and transmission of knowledge
- Social relevance of knowledge
- Establishing link with the society through extension work
- Continuous efforts to upgrade knowledge
- Freedom of inquiry
- Desire for excellence
- Willingness to collaborate
- Critically analyzing the events
- Willingness to take criticism
- Initiating the innovative activities
- Possessing skills for planning and guiding the activities
- Motivating the students and the communities
- Favorable attitude to execute the activities
- Having problem solving skills
- Knowledge of socio-economic and cultural status and sensitivities of the communities involved.

12. Implications for Implementation:

Continuing Education as an empowering tool for the Hospitality and Tourism Educators to facilitate taking up extension-based work.

An extension educator must simultaneously wear multiple hats - that of a teacher, guide, friend and philosopher. To be a successful extension educator, one must not only have a sound knowledge and understanding of the subject, but also an interest and ability to work for and with community people. The profession, while challenging, can also be very satisfying. Knowledge in every field is last changing. There is a continuous need to develop the skills and competences. Constantly striving to learn about new and evolving knowledge or to review existing concepts and techniques, is termed as 'Continuing Education'. The Continuing Education gives an opportunity for the educators to interact with colleagues and serves to open up knowledge areas unvisited. It promotes a higher level of professionalism in the concerned domain worldwide. For attaining necessary skills or imbibing socioeconomic and cultural knowledge and to be able to plan appropriate extension activities, the educators may need to resort to continuing education methods, taking up online study or distance learning, attending group discussion, workshops or seminars or conferences or summer schools or meetings (of learned societies) or training programmes as also taking up a short-term course could be some of the Continuing Education methods. No more can teachers confine their role within the four walls of educational institutions. They have to feel the pulse of the community and try to help them solve their problems. They are to be social engineers who can mold the destiny of the Nation, in and outside the classrooms.

13. Conclusion and Recommendation

There is a lack of proper attention, awareness and interest in Extension Education. The linkage between teachings, research and extension is weak, particularly because extension is still not well recognized and used properly as the other two academic functions of the University (Warner *et al.* 1996). The

knowledge generated by research often gets obsolete by the time it is disseminated through education / teaching and finally trickles down to community members and practitioners through extension due to big lapse of time. The universities should consider this problem seriously and should reform their academic activities to strengthen the links between research, teaching and extension. E-Extension or Internet aided extension networks have to be materialized as nerve centers for dissemination of technical know-how. There is need of change in extension from Transfer of Technology Mode to Technology Application Mode by initiating Group approach and community group's participatory approach of Extension activities. Inclusion of Community-based organizations, stake-holders in Extension Formation and training of self-help groups and extension through rural location - specific knowledge center would serve the need of present extension service. Extension Education and training needs focus on need-based, problem-solving, skill-based vocational enterprises for self-employment for rural youth. There is dire need to establish linkages among extension education, continuing education, non-formal education, distance education and vocational education, so that each support and strengthens the efforts of the other and vice-versa. It is necessary to mention here that formation of commodity specific extension kiosk on all niche tourism products (viz agri tourism, rural tourism, farm tourism, village tourism etc.) and value addition enterprises are required. Distance education and technology enabled learning for community-entrepreneurs need to be explored and strengthened through television, radio, interactive audio and video systems, besides print and programmed learning materials which would be the distinguishing feature of extension teaching and learning process.

References

- Buckley. R.C. (2004). Skilled commercial adventure: The edge of tourism. In: Singh TV (eds). *New horizons in tourism*. Oxford: CAB International. 37-48.
- Despotovic. M. Maksimovic. I. & Pejatovic. A. (2004). *Methodology of Curriculum Development in Vocational Education and Training and Adult Education*. Retrieved March 12. 2015. from **Vocational Education and Training Reform Programme website**: <http://www.vetserbia.edu.rs/policyandstrategy%20papers.htm>
- Dieke. P.I.J.C. (2003). Tourism in Africa's economic development: Policy implications. *Management Decisions*, 41(3), 287-295
- Fenley. J.M and SKI Williams (1964): background for extension war. Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources: Extension Training Manual Bulletin No 3 Franz. N, (2007). Adult education theories: Informing Cooperative Extension's transformation. *Journal of Extension*. 45. Retrieved April 02. 2015. from <http://www.joe.org/joe/2007February7>
- Gerosa. V. (2003). Pro-poor growth strategies in Africa - tourism: a viable option for proper **growth in Africa**/ Paper prepared for the Economic Commission for Africa Expert Group Meeting, **Kampala**.
- Hanqin. Z.Q.& Terrv. L. (2004). Human resources issues in the development of tourism in

- China: evidence from Heilongjiang Province. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. 16. 45-51.
- Howel. R. Uysal. M. (1987). Tourism education for developing countries. *Tourism Management*, 8. 62-4. IGNOU (n.d.). *Curriculum Transaction*. Study Material of PG Diploma in Higher Education (Course Code 104). Unit 15. Block 4. p. 42. New Delhi: Indira Gandhi National Open University.
- [10] IGNOI (n.d.). *Management of Extension. Community Centred and Co-curricular Activities*, Study Material of PG Diploma in Higher Education (Course Code 104). Unit 12. Block 3. pp. 55 64. New Delhi: Indira Gandhi National Open University.
- ILO: Development and Challenges in the Hospitality and Tourism Sector. Issues paper for discussion at the Global Dialogue Forum for the Hotels. Catering. Tourism Sector (Geneva: 2010) Kelly. A. V. (2004). *The curriculum: Theory and practice* (5th ed.). London: Stage.
- Kothari. A. (2007). Tourism. Wildlife and Communities. *The Hindu-Survey of the Environment*, 28 (4), 9-14.
- Legacy. J.. & Wells. J. (1987). A national study of recommended curricula for extension education methods classes and student internship programs. *Journal of Agricultural Education*. 28(4). 9-14.
- Muhanna. E. (2007). The contribution of sustainable tourism development in poverty alleviation of local communities in South Africa. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality and Tourism*. 6(1). 37-67.
- National Job Bank. (2008). *Jobs in extension. outreach, research & higher education*. Retrieved April 02. 2015. from http://jobs.joe.org/search_list.php
- Relly. P., & Koch, E. (2002). *Case study assessment Jackal berry Lodge- Thornybush Game Reserve*. National Responsible Tourism Guidelines for the South African Tourism Sector, Application of the Guidelines to the Nature-Based Tourism Sector Report to DFID.
- Sanyal, B. C. (2005). The Role of Higher Education in obtaining EFA goals with particular focus on developing countries. *UNESCO Forum on Higher Education, Research; Knowledge*. 12.
- Saville, ATI (1965): *Extension in Rural Communities*: London Oxford University Press Pp3. Scheer, S. D., Ferrari. 1 M. Earnest. G. & Connors. J. J. (2006). Preparing extension professionals: The Ohio State University's model of extension education. Retrieved March 14. 2015. from <http://v\wwjoe.org/joe/2006august/alp.shtml>
- Schmiesing. R. J. & Safrit. R. I). (2007). "4-11 youth development professionals" perceptions of the importance of and their current level of competence with selected volunteer management competencies. *Journal of Extension*, 45(3). Retrieved April 02, 2015, from <http://7www.joe.org/joe/2007june/rb1p.shtml>

- Sinclair, D. (2003). Developing indigenous tourism: challenges for the Guianas. *International Journal of cotemporary Hospitality Management*. 15. 140-6
- Torres. R.. & Momsen. J.IT (2004). Challenges and potential for linking tourism and agriculture to achieve pro-poor tourism objectives. *Progress in Development Studies*. 4(4). 294-318.
- UNESCO. 1996. Learning: The Treasure Within. The Report to UNESCO of the International Commission on Education for the Twenty First Century chaired by Jacques Delors. Paris. UNESCO.
- Watson. S. & Drummond. D. (2002). A strategic perspective to human resource development in Scottish tourism, *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. 14. 253-254.
- Wikipedia. 2015. Agricultural extension. The free encyclopedia. The Wikimedia foundation. Inc. USA: Retrieved April. 02, 2015: <http://en.wikipeclia.org/wiki/Agricoltura1extension>
<http://www.academy\projects.org>: Retrieved March. 10. 2015